

Indonesian Pragmatics Marker *ayo*

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ABSTRACT

Indonesia has a large number of pragmatics markers used as a reflection of Indonesian cultural values. The study tries to find out the usage of Indonesian *ayo* with its grammatical meaning that is related to the joining phrases and sentences. The study used textual analysis of the Covid 19 health protocol shared online by local government agencies. The study finds that the users are related to the speech situation of asking people to obey and to stay alert to the Covid-19 health protocol. It also serves the emotive or expressive function of government leaders in maintaining the relationships between the leaders and the community while still maintaining politeness and solidarity among speakers. The study concludes that *Ayo* has a significant role as the pragmatics marker on the shared text online.

Keywords: *pragmatics markers, ayo, covid 19 health protocol, government, and the community.*

Backgrounds.

The interpretation of utterances is a complex task. Hearers have to rely on several types of knowledge to grasp the meaning of what is ostensively communicated. Syntax, semantics, and pragmatics are three types of linguistic knowledge that are brought to bear in the comprehension of linguistic meaning. In other words, both the inherent meaning of linguistic expressions and meaning derived from contextual factors are salient for comprehension. (Andersen, 2000)

Pragmatic markers have an important role in achieving mutual understanding in conversations. They often "express speakers' attitude towards addressee" (Wierzbicka, 1991) and give the hearer a communicative clue as to how to interpret utterance (Fraser, 1990; Foolen, 2011; Han, 2011). Brinton (1996) proposes several characteristics of pragmatic particles as follows.

Phonological and lexical features

- (a) they are short and phonologically reduced;
- (b) they form a separate tone group;
- (c) they are marginal forms and difficult to place in a traditional word class;

Syntactic features

- (d) they are restricted to the sentence-initial position;
- (e) they occur outside the syntactic structure or are only loosely attached to it;
- (f) they are optional;

Semantic features

(g) they have little or no propositional meaning;

Functional features

(h) they are multi-functional, operating on several linguistic levels;

Sociolinguistic and stylistic features

(i) they are a feature of oral rather than written discourse and are associated with Informality;

(j) they appear with high frequency;

(k) they are stylistically stigmatized; and

(l) they are gender-specific and more typical of women's speech.

Some studies emphasize the role of markers as devices for signaling intratextual (sequential) structure (e.g. Schiffrin 1987; Fraser 1998), others focus on their function of expressing speaker attitude (e.g. Andersen & Fretheim 2000), and yet others emphasize their role as devices for acknowledging and highlighting the speaker-hearer relationship and increasing politeness (e.g. Cameron et al. 1989; Stenström 1989, 1994; Holmes 1995).

Pragmatic markers generally tell the hearer what sort of inferential processes the utterance interpretation involves and are used to manipulate the process of context selection. They make explicit the relation that exists between a communicated assumption and the interlocutors' cognitive environment. Markers may be used not only to express how the speaker perceives the information encoded by a proposition but also how she perceives the communicative situation and her conversational and social relation with the hearer. Sometimes, but not always, markers also express the relationship that exists between units of discourse (e.g. propositions). It makes sense to single out certain markers that have an interactional capacity and are hearer orientated (take the hearer's perspective, express empathy towards him, or attempt to draw him into the conversation) as opposed to those that lack such a capacity but are primarily oriented towards the speaker's own beliefs and attitudes.

Indonesian has a large number of discourse markers, which may be defined as particles or phrases used in the interactional and informational organization of a conversation (Schiffrin, 1987). The two most frequent are the agreement markers *ya* and *kan*. *Ya* is a shortened form of the affirmative particle *iya*, while *kan* is a shortened form of *bukan?* One of the negative particles of Indonesian. The two are used both interrogatively and non-interrogatively. The high frequency of this type of usage in Indonesian conversation can be seen as a reflection of Indonesian cultural values, which place a premium on maintaining the appearance of cooperative behavior. (Wouk, 1998:2001).

Before Wouk's investigation, Wolff (1980) studied the particle *kan* and found that it has three main functions. It serves first of all as an *agreement marker* and functions like *tag questions* in English. It is also an indication of conjoint knowledge, which is presumably on par with Holmes' (1986) *you know*. Lastly, it can also be used as a request for verification. Wouk (1998) reassesses these findings by studying Indonesian colloquial data. She found that the particle *kan* is mostly used as an *emphatic marker* and to some extent as a *topic introduction*. Indonesian markers were also explored by Sari (2007) who found seven Indonesian particles;

kan, ya, kok, lho, dong, sih, and deh, and by Kulsum (2012) who studied phrases of *iya deh* and *iya dong*.

While it is widely agreed that such expressions play a variety of important roles in utterance interpretation, there is disagreement concerning such fundamental issues as how the discourse marker class should be delimited, whether the items in question comprise a unified grammatical category, what type of meaning they express, and the sense in which such expressions may be said to relate elements of a discourse. (Schourup, 1999).

During the past two decades research concerning the functions and uses of what Longacre (1976) still called 'mystery particles' has developed into an impressive field of its own, resulting in extensive research on pragmatic particles in various languages. Accordingly, by now some of these 'mystery particles' have lost some of their mysterious characters.

Holker (1991) lists four basic features that characterize discourse markers (or pragmatic markers, as he calls them). (1) they do not affect the truth conditions of an utterance; (2) they do not add anything to the propositional content of an utterance; (3) they are related to the speech situation and not to the situation talked about; and (4) they have an emotive, expressive function rather than a referential, denotative, or cognitive function.

Schiffrin (1987) makes the following tentative suggestions as to what conditions allow an expression to be used as a marker.

- a. It has to be syntactically detachable from a sentence
- b. It has to be commonly used in an initial position of an utterance
- c. It has to have a range of prosodic contours (e.g. tonic stress followed by a pause,
- d. phonological reduction)
- e. It has to be able to operate at both local and global levels of discourse, and on different
- f. planes of discourse
- g. This means that it has to have no meaning, a vague meaning, or to be reflexive (of the
- h. language of the speaker)

Jucker and Ziv (1998) cite the four conditions for pragmatic markers suggested by Hölker (1991):

- a. They do not affect the truth conditions of an utterance
- b. They do not add anything to the propositional content of an utterance
- c. They are related to the speech situation and not to the situation talked about
- d. They have an emotive, expressive function rather than a referential, denotative, or
- e. cognitive function.

Further characteristics adapted from Brinton's (1996) longer list reordered and abbreviated by Jucker and Ziv (1998) and Andersen (2000) include the following, among others which are similar to those listed by Schiffrin

- a. They occur outside the syntactic structure or are only loosely attached to it
- b. They are optional rather than obligatory features
- c. They are features of oral rather than written discourse

- d. They are short and (often) phonologically reduced
- e. They are stylistically stigmatized
- f. They constitute a heterogeneous set of forms that are difficult to place within a
- g. traditional word class (including items like *ah*, *actually*, *and*, *just*, *like*, *now*, *really*,
- h. *well*, *I mean*, *I think and you know*)
- i. They have little or no propositional meaning.

Andersen (2000) argues against the importance traditionally given to non-propositionally as an essential property of pragmatic markers, preferring to consider this feature as usual but not essential. More pertinently, “the label ‘pragmatic’ is meant to suggest a relatively low degree of lexical specificity and a high degree of context-sensitivity.” Furthermore, pragmatic markers may indicate speaker attitudes, carry out speech act functions or serve to increase politeness and solidarity among speakers.

Methods

The data for this research was gathered during the height of the Covid-19 pandemic when the alert notice was distributed online via social media. The investigation was conducted based on online alert notices among Indonesians as part of public policy where policymakers should balance the rights of individuals and the promotion of public good while carefully considering the epidemiological, programmatic, and legal issues. (Kaufman, 2021)

Ayo

Indonesian *ayo* only has its grammatical meaning and has no lexical meaning. It is classified as functional words (*kata tugas*) which its meaning are related to the joining phrases and sentences. It is also called interjection as parts of functional words which expressed the speaker's moods as amaze, sad, wonder, and disgust. Interjection *ayo* has the meaning of invitation and has synonymous variation as *mari*. (Moeliono, 2017).

Picture 1. Ayo Bersiap! dan Ikuti Tahapan Vaksinasi Covid-19.

Vaksin Coronavac, Vaccine Covid-19, dan Vac2 Bio Produksi Sinovac Lifescience .Co telah dinyatakan Halal dan Suci oleh Majelis Ulama Indonesia

Ayo Bersiap! dan Ikuti Tahapan Vaksinasi COVID-19

Hotline WhatsApp
Vaksinasi COVID-19
Kabupaten Tangerang

0813-154-11-937
(dr. Secunia Suswanti)

0812-103-1343
(dr. M. Fandi Hiki)

0813-851-66-711
(Toni S.KW, M.Si)

Wahasan Putih, Ekonomi Bangkit

PERPANJANGAN PEMBATASAN KEGIATAN MASYARAKAT (PENTING) PADA WILAYAH KABUPATEN TANGERANG (26 Januari Tangerang Nomor 443/276/Sgubab/2021)

26 JANUARI - 8 FEBRUARI 2021

<p>Menzahuti Protokol Kesehatan COVID-19</p> <p>Implementasi di setiap orang, di semua lokasi, dan di semua waktu. Penegakan dan pemantauan dilakukan oleh Tim Task Force.</p>	<p>Mengurangi Aktivitas di Luar Rumah</p> <p>Minimal untuk melaksanakan ibadah, keperluan kebutuhan vital dan keperluan kesehatan diri.</p>	<p>Perkantoran WFH : 25%</p> <p>Perkantoran Perseorangan Lebih Kecil</p>	<p>Proses Belajar Mengajar</p> <p>3 Waktu / 3 Tahap Pembelajaran dengan Metode Belajar</p>
<p>Sektor Esensial</p> <p>Perdagangan, Jasa, Industri, dan Jasa. Sektor ini akan beroperasi dengan kapasitas maksimal 50%.</p>	<p>Pusat Perbelanjaan (Mall) & Pertokoan</p> <p>dan Perumahan</p> <p>Pukul 16.00-20.00 WIB</p>	<p>Rumah Makan</p> <p>dan Perumahan</p> <p>Pukul 16.00-20.00 WIB</p>	<p>Tempat Hiburan Malam</p> <p>dan Perumahan</p> <p>Pukul 16.00-20.00 WIB</p>
<p>Penyedia Konstruksi</p> <p>dan Perumahan</p> <p>100% Kapasitas</p>	<p>Kegiatan Keagamaan di Rumah Ibadah</p> <p>dan Perumahan</p> <p>50% Kapasitas</p>	<p>Kegiatan Fasilitas Umum/ Sosial Budaya</p> <p>dan Perumahan</p> <p>50% Kapasitas</p>	<p>Angkutan Orang</p> <p>dan Perumahan</p> <p>50% Kapasitas</p>
<p>Satuan Tugas</p> <p>dan Perumahan</p> <p>50% Kapasitas</p>	<p>Di Wilayah Desa</p> <p>dan Perumahan</p> <p>50% Kapasitas</p>	<p>Di Wilayah Desa</p> <p>dan Perumahan</p> <p>50% Kapasitas</p>	<p>Di Wilayah Desa</p> <p>dan Perumahan</p> <p>50% Kapasitas</p>

Ingat 4M: MEMAKAI MASKER, MENJAGA JARAK, MEMUCI TANGAN, MEMALUKAN KERUMUMAN

PENGADUAN PPKM 0882-896-700-50

Source: <https://covid19.tangerangkab.go.id/infografis?page=33>

Picture 2. Ayo Vaksinasi Covid-19.

PEMERINTAH PROVINSI SUMATERA SELATAN

AYO VAKSINASI COVID-19

H. HERMAN DERU
GUBERNUR SUMATERA SELATAN

MENJADI ORANG PERTAMA DI SUMSEL YANG MELAKUKAN VAKSINASI COVID-19 PADA HARI KAMIS TANGGAL 14 JANUARI 2021

bakohumasprovsumsel

TAHAP I JANUARI - APRIL 2021

- TENAGA KESEHATAN
- PETUGAS PUBLIK
- LANSIA

TAHAP II APRIL 2021 - MARET 2022

- MASYARAKAT RENTAN DAERAH DENGAN RISIKO PENULARAN TERTINGGI
- MASYARAKAT LAINNYA PENDIDATAN KLASTER SESUAI KETERSEDIAAN VAKSIN

MELINDUNGI DIRI, KELUARGA DAN SESAMA

#SUKSESKANVAKSINASI
#VAKSINIOLOSUJUKINDIS
#SUMSELBERSATUMELAWANCORONAVIRUS

PATUHI PROTOKOL KESEHATAN COVID-19

3M MEMAKAI MASKER
MEMUCI TANGAN
MENJAGA JARAK

H. HERMAN DERU
GUBERNUR SUMATERA SELATAN

Source: <http://corona.sumselprov.go.id/index.php?module=home&id=1>
Accessed on 4 January 2022

Picture 3. Ayo pakai masker! Kesehatan Pulih, Ekonomi Bangkit.

Source: https://covid19.sumutprov.go.id/gallery?per_page=11
Accessed on 4 January 2022

Picture 4. Ayo Jaga Jarak.

Source: <https://belukab.go.id/wp-content/uploads/jaga-jarak.png>
 Accessed on 4 January 2022

Picture 5. Payo kanti-kanti !! Kito jago diri dan keluarga kito dari virus korona.

Source: https://jambiprov.go.id/img_galeri/95WhatsApp%20Image%202021-08-02%20at%2008.59.26.jpeg

Accessed on 4 January 2022

Discussion

Indonesian pragmatics marker *Ayo* as stated in the data

Picture 1. Ayo Bersiap! dan Ikuti Tahapan Vaksinasi Covid-19.

Picture 2. Ayo Vaksinasi Covid-19.

Picture 3. Ayo pakai masker! Kesehatan Pulih, Ekonomi Bangkit.

Picture 4. Ayo Jaga Jarak.

Picture 5. Payo kanti-kanti!! Kito jago diri dan keluarga kito dari virus korona.

The (Pictures 1, 2, 3, 4, 5) can be the best example of Brinton (1996) who proposes several characteristics of pragmatic particles as they are often short and phonologically reduced and they are optional rather than obligatory, which means that their absence in conversation “does not render a sentence ungrammatical and/ or unintelligible”.

The (Pictures 1, 2, 3, 4, 5) can also best example of Jucker and Ziv (1998) cite the conditions for pragmatic markers suggested by Hölker (1991) as they do not add anything to the propositional content of an utterance, they are related to the speech situation and not to the situation talked about and finally, they have an emotive, expressive function rather than a referential, denotative, or cognitive function.

The (Pictures 1, 2, 3, 4, 5) are related to the speech situation of asking people to obey and to stay alert to the covid-19 protocol rules because of the potential dangers of ignoring the protocols. Besides they have the emotive or expressive function of government leaders in maintaining the relationships between the leaders and the community while still serving to increase politeness and solidarity among speakers.

Conclusion

The usage of particle *ayo* proves the theory of Brinton (1996), Jucker and Ziv (1998), which are related to the speech situation of asking people to obey and to stay alert to the covid-19 protocol rules because of the potential dangers of ignoring the protocols. Just as vaccine mandates are legitimized by reducing the risk of one person passing an infection to others. In general community settings, mandates may be used as a strategy to increase vaccination coverage more broadly. Because they are more coercive than other interventions to increase vaccination coverage, mandates demand stronger ethical justification. Policymakers should balance the rights of individuals and the promotion of public good while carefully considering the epidemiological, programmatic and legal issues. (Kaufman, 2021) When considering the

benefits of vaccination, it may help to highlight the protection from vaccination for individuals and those around them, and to ask them what else they may value about being vaccinated.

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